

Report on the third needs analysis results

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The third needs analysis results concerning "Challenges and opportunities of the technology transfer and sustainable entrepreneurship in open innovation ecosystem"

Need analysis represents the part of the researchers' activities that follow the return phase, together with Focus group and Delphi study. Therefore, this time, after each secondment to SME4, as EU non-academic partner, upon returning to their home country, talents presented the key issues and ideas from secondment phase and, together with researchers identified the situation and assess the needs of the business community in each widening country.

Needs analysis is aimed at getting information about technology transfer, open innovation, and intellectual property rights from the business community's point of view. It is based on the questionnaire, which represents the result of the Delphi study. During the period June – July, 2024, the questionnaire was formulated and then used for collecting data. Data were collected in all four widening countries: Serbia, Albania, Bosnia & Herzegovina, and North Macedonia.

Needs analysis should show what issues concerning technology transfer, open innovation, sustainable entrepreneurship and intellectual property rights are considered the most challenging by overall business community, regardless of the industry type or size. The idea is to use the analysis results to realize how should academic community and regional innovation ecosystem provide support to the business community. Final destination is proposal of training programmes' topics that will be composed under each Center for entrepreneurship and innovation (EI center).

Sample structure

Research refers to the sample of 100 companies. In each widening country were collected 25 questionnaires. The following table describe the sample according to company size in each country.

Table 1: Number of companies per country

		Company size			Total
		Large	Medium	Small	
Country	Albania	16	8	1	25
	Bosnia and Herzegovina	8	11	6	25
	North Macedonia	5	10	10	25
	Serbia	4	10	11	25
Total		33	39	28	100

Source: Authors' presentation

From the total number of companies in the sample, the majority refers to medium companies (39), then large (33) and small (28).

Table 2: Company size

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Size	Large	33	33.0	33.0	33.0
	Medium	39	39.0	39.0	72.0
	Small	28	28.0	28.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Authors' presentation

Taking into account the company's activities, the largest participation in the sample has companies from the fields of Information and Communications (34%), Manufacturing Industry (30%) and Financial and insurance activities (8%).

Table 3: Company's activity

Activity	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Area C: Manufacturing Industry	30	30.0	30.0	30.0
Area D: Production and supply of electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning	4	4.0	4.0	34.0
Area E: Water supply, sewerage, waste management and environmental rehabilitation (remediation) activities	2	2.0	2.0	36.0
Area F: Construction	3	3.0	3.0	39.0
Area G: Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	1	1.0	1.0	40.0
Area J: Information and Communications	34	34.0	34.0	74.0
Area K: Financial and insurance activities	8	8.0	8.0	82.0
Area L: Real estate business	2	2.0	2.0	84.0
Area M: Professional, scientific and technical activities	1	1.0	1.0	85.0
Area N: Administrative and auxiliary service activities	1	1.0	1.0	86.0
Area O: Public administration and defence, compulsory social insurance	3	3.0	3.0	89.0
Area P: Education	3	3.0	3.0	92.0
Area Q: Health care and social work activities	5	5.0	5.0	97.0
Area S: Other service activities	1	1.0	1.0	98.0
Area U: Organization of extraterritorial organizations and bodies	2	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Authors' presentation

Considering the gender, the largest number of companies is managed by men, in 61% of cases.

Table 4: Gender structure of respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	39	39.0	39.0	39.0
	Male	61	61.0	61.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Authors' presentation

The largest percentage of managers have Higher professional education - II cycle of studies - social and humanities (42%), Higher professional education - I cycle of studies - social and humanities (19%) and Higher professional education - II cycle of studies - technical sciences (18%). Only 1% of managers in the sample has Secondary education.

Table 5: Respondent's education

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Higher professional education - I cycle of studies - natural sciences	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Higher professional education - I cycle of studies - social and humanities	19	19.0	19.0	20.0
	Higher professional education - I cycle of studies - technical sciences	11	11.0	11.0	31.0
	Higher professional education - II cycle of studies - natural sciences	3	3.0	3.0	34.0
	Higher professional education - II cycle of studies - social and humanities	42	42.0	42.0	76.0
	Higher professional education - II cycle of studies - technical sciences	18	18.0	18.0	94.0
	Higher professional education - III cycle of studies - natural sciences	1	1.0	1.0	95.0
	Higher professional education - III cycle of studies - social and humanities	4	4.0	4.0	99.0
	Secondary education	1	1.0	1.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Statistical analysis

According to the research results and descriptive statistical analysis, all tested variables were rated very high (Table). The average rating of all is higher than 4, except: 1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [c] Government bodies that support funding and policy] (3.95); 7. How do you perform R&D activities? [a] Collaboration with universities and external partners] (3.87); 7. How do you perform R&D activities? [b] Establishing research centers focused on innovation] (3.72); and 8. How do you implement innovative solutions in your company (organization)? [b] We engage external experts to support innovation] (3.75). The highest average ratings achieved for the following variables: 3. How much are the following factors important for successful commercialization of innovations? [c] Product adaptation to market needs] (4.56); 3. How much are the following aspects important for the implementation of open innovation strategies? [c] Leadership and management support] (4.54) and 3. How much are the following aspects important for the implementation of open innovation strategies? [a] Innovation culture within the organization] (4.48). Also, the standard deviation shows a high degree of agreement between the managers on the ratings of the tested variables. In this regard, the conclusion is that all variables are extremely important, as well as that the right variables were selected during the design of the survey questionnaire. The greatest disagreements, or the highest standard deviation, were recorded for the variables that were simultaneously the lowest rated by the managers.

Table 6: Descriptive statistics of tested variables

Questions	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [a] Universities and research institutions]	100	4.3000	.85870
1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [b] Start-ups, small and medium-sized enterprises, and large corporations]	100	4.3200	.78983
1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [c] Government bodies that support funding and policy]	100	3.9500	1.04809
1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [d] Investors]	100	4.2500	.90314
2. How much are the following aspects important for the implementation of open innovation strategies? [a] Innovation culture within the organization]	100	4.4800	.70324
2. How much are the following aspects important for the implementation of open innovation strategies? [b] Technological infrastructure]	100	4.3900	.66507
2. How much are the following aspects important for the implementation of open innovation strategies? [c] Leadership and management support]	100	4.5400	.70238

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3. How much are the following factors important for successful commercialization of innovations? [a) Market access and marketing orientation of the organization]	100	4.4500	.65713
3. How much are the following factors important for successful commercialization of innovations? [b) Intellectual property protection (patents protection, copyrights, trade secrets, industrial design rights, trademarks and branding)]	100	4.2400	.87755
3. How much are the following factors important for successful commercialization of innovations? [c) Product adaptation to market needs]	100	4.5600	.60836
3. How much are the following factors important for successful commercialization of innovations? [d) Partnerships with industrial entities]	100	4.1900	.89550
4. What are the main challenges of technology transfer and sustainable entrepreneurship in the open innovation ecosystem in your country? [a) Insufficient financial resources and investments]	100	4.2100	.86801
4. What are the main challenges of technology transfer and sustainable entrepreneurship in the open innovation ecosystem in your country? [b) Weak collaboration between industry and research institutions]	100	4.2100	.89098
5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [a) Availability of grants and subsidies]	100	4.1900	.84918
5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [b) Opportunities for private investment]	100	4.2200	.75985
5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [c) Access to angles' investors, venture capital and crowdfunding]	100	4.0300	.86987
5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [d) Tax incentives for research and development]	100	4.1200	.85611
5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [e) Costs and return on investment]	100	4.3500	.80873
6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [a) Tax credits and deductions for research and development activities]	100	4.0000	.94281
6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [b) Grants and funding programs for collaborative research projects]	100	4.2200	.91652
6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [c) Subsidies for technology commercialization efforts]	100	4.0300	.95827
6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [d)	100	4.0300	.94767

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Regulatory support and streamlined processes for intellectual property protection]			
7. How do you perform R&D activities? [a] Collaboration with universities and external partners]	100	3.8700	1.19473
7. How do you perform R&D activities? [b] Establishing research centers focused on innovation]	100	3.7200	1.18134
7. How do you perform R&D activities? [c] Conducting market research to guide product development]	100	4.2100	.76930
7. How do you perform R&D activities? [d] Participation in collaborative research projects with global partners]	100	4.0700	1.03724
8. How do you implement innovative solutions in your company (organization)? [a] We use internal R&D teams for developing new solutions]	100	4.2600	.87178
8. How do you implement innovative solutions in your company (organization)? [b] We engage external experts to support innovation]	100	3.7500	1.04809
9. How much are the following legal and regulatory factors important for the intellectual property protection? [c] National intellectual property laws]	100	4.2700	.82701
9. How much are the following legal and regulatory factors important for the intellectual property protection? [d] International agreements and conventions]	100	4.3000	.78496
9. How much are the following legal and regulatory factors important for the intellectual property protection? [e] Administrative procedures for rights protection]	100	4.2900	.80773
10a. How significant are the following obstacles in the intellectual property protection system? [a] High costs and complexity of the patent system]	100	4.2000	.88763
10a. How significant are the following obstacles in the intellectual property protection system? [b] Lack of awareness and education on intellectual property rights]	100	4.2100	.91337
10a. How significant are the following obstacles in the intellectual property protection system? [c] Insufficient enforcement mechanisms for IP protection]	100	4.1800	.92529
10a. How significant are the following obstacles in the intellectual property protection system? [d] Lack of harmonization with international IP standards]	100	4.0200	.94259
10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [a] Harmonizing national IP laws with international standards]	100	4.1600	.86129
10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [b] Encouraging innovation while ensuring fair competition]	100	4.4200	.69892
10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [c] Addressing piracy and counterfeiting effectively]	100	4.3800	.73553

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10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [d] Promoting cross-border cooperation and information sharing]	100	4.1800	.91431
10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [e] Balancing the interests of IP holders with public access to knowledge]	100	4.0300	.84632

Source: Authors' presentation

Taking into account the size of the company and the average ratings of the analysed variables, it is concluded that all variables are very important regardless of the size of the company since average ratings in most cases are greater than 4. The following variables got the lowest ratings: 1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [c] Government bodies that support funding and policy] (3.75 and only in the case of small companies); 5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [c] Access to angels' investors, venture capital and crowdfunding] (3.93 and only in the case of small companies); 6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [a] Tax credits and deductions for research and development activities] (3.85 only in the case of large companies); 6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [c] Subsidies for technology commercialization efforts] (3.88 only in the case of large companies); 7. How do you perform R&D activities? [a] Collaboration with universities and external partners] (3.88 and 3.67 in case of large and medium companies respectively); 7. How do you perform R&D activities? [b] Establishing research centers focused on innovation] (3.59 and 3.75 in case of medium and small companies respectively); 7. How do you perform R&D activities? [d] Participation in collaborative research projects with global partners] (3.96 only in the case of small companies); 8. How do you implement innovative solutions in your company (organization)? [b] We engage external experts to support innovation] (3.97, 3.49 and 3.86 in case of large, medium and small companies respectively); 10a. How significant are the following obstacles in the intellectual property protection system? [d] Lack of harmonization with international IP standards] (3.86), 10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [a] Harmonizing national IP laws with international standards] (3.93), 10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [e] Balancing the interests of IP holders with public access to knowledge] (3.89) only in the case of small companies. The biggest discrepancy in ratings between companies was found for variable 2. How much are the following aspects important for the implementation of open innovation strategies? [c] Leadership and management support] (4.70 only in case of large companies).

Table 7: Average ratings by company size

Company size	Large		Medium		Small	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [a] Universities and research institutions]	4.3636	.65279	4.1795	1.07292	4.3929	.73733

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1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [b) Start-ups, small and medium-sized enterprises, and large corporations]	4.3030	.80951	4.2821	.72361	4.3929	.87514
1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [c) Government bodies that support funding and policy]	4.0303	1.10354	4.0256	1.01274	3.7500	1.04083
1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [d) Investors]	4.2424	.86712	4.2821	.88700	4.2143	.99469
2. How much are the following aspects important for the implementation of open innovation strategies? [a) Innovation culture within the organization]	4.5152	.66714	4.5128	.72081	4.3929	.73733
2. How much are the following aspects important for the implementation of open innovation strategies? [b) Technological infrastructure]	4.3939	.60927	4.4615	.60027	4.2857	.80999
2. How much are the following aspects important for the implementation of open innovation strategies? [c) Leadership and management support]	4.6970	.52944	4.5385	.64262	4.3571	.91142
3. How much are the following factors important for successful commercialization of innovations? [a) Market access and marketing orientation of the organization]	4.4242	.61392	4.4103	.67738	4.5357	.69293
3. How much are the following factors important for successful commercialization of innovations? [b) Intellectual property protection (patents protection, copyrights, trade secrets, industrial design rights, trademarks and branding)]	4.3333	.85391	4.3846	.67338	3.9286	1.08623
3. How much are the following factors important for successful commercialization of	4.5758	.56071	4.5641	.59802	4.5357	.69293

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innovations? [c] Product adaptation to market needs]						
3. How much are the following factors important for successful commercialization of innovations? [d] Partnerships with industrial entities]	4.1515	.87039	4.2564	.88013	4.1429	.97046
4. What are the main challenges of technology transfer and sustainable entrepreneurship in the open innovation ecosystem in your country? [a] Insufficient financial resources and investments]	4.1212	.96039	4.3077	.76619	4.1786	.90487
4. What are the main challenges of technology transfer and sustainable entrepreneurship in the open innovation ecosystem in your country? [b] Weak collaboration between industry and research institutions]	4.2727	.83937	4.2051	.89382	4.1429	.97046
5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [a] Availability of grants and subsidies]	4.0909	.84275	4.2821	.85682	4.1786	.86297
5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [b] Opportunities for private investment]	4.1818	.76871	4.3590	.74294	4.0714	.76636
5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [c] Access to angles' investors, venture capital and crowdfunding]	4.1212	.81997	4.0256	.77755	3.9286	1.05158
5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [d] Tax incentives for research and development]	4.0000	.79057	4.1026	.82062	4.2857	.97590
5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [e] Costs and return on investment]	4.3939	.74747	4.3590	.77755	4.2857	.93718

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6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [a] Tax credits and deductions for research and development activities]	3.8485	1.06423	4.1282	.80064	4.0000	.98131
6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [b] Grants and funding programs for collaborative research projects]	4.1212	.92728	4.2564	.90954	4.2857	.93718
6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [c] Subsidies for technology commercialization efforts]	3.8788	.92728	4.0000	.97333	4.2500	.96705
6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [d] Regulatory support and streamlined processes for intellectual property protection]	4.0909	.97991	4.0000	.91766	4.0000	.98131
7. How do you perform R&D activities? [a] Collaboration with universities and external partners]	3.8788	1.24392	3.6667	1.30451	4.1429	.93152
7. How do you perform R&D activities? [b] Establishing research centers focused on innovation]	3.8485	1.17583	3.5897	1.22942	3.7500	1.14261
7. How do you perform R&D activities? [c] Conducting market research to guide product development]	4.1515	.79535	4.2821	.79302	4.1786	.72283
7. How do you perform R&D activities? [d] Participation in collaborative research projects with global partners]	4.1212	.89294	4.1026	1.07103	3.9643	1.17006

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8. How do you implement innovative solutions in your company (organization)? [a] We use internal R&D teams for developing new solutions]	4.1515	.97215	4.3077	.89307	4.3214	.72283
8. How do you implement innovative solutions in your company (organization)? [b] We engage external experts to support innovation]	3.9697	.88335	3.4872	1.16691	3.8571	1.00791
9. How much are the following legal and regulatory factors important for the intellectual property protection? [c] National intellectual property laws]	4.3333	.88976	4.3333	.73747	4.1071	.87514
9. How much are the following legal and regulatory factors important for the intellectual property protection? [d] International agreements and conventions]	4.3636	.69903	4.3590	.70663	4.1429	.97046
9. How much are the following legal and regulatory factors important for the intellectual property protection? [e] Administrative procedures for rights protection]	4.1818	.76871	4.4872	.68333	4.1429	.97046
10a. How significant are the following obstacles in the intellectual property protection system? [a] High costs and complexity of the patent system]	4.1818	.80834	4.2564	.88013	4.1429	1.00791
10a. How significant are the following obstacles in the intellectual property protection system? [b] Lack of awareness and education on intellectual property rights]	4.3636	.78335	4.1538	.96077	4.1071	.99403
10a. How significant are the following obstacles in the intellectual property protection system? [c] Insufficient enforcement mechanisms for IP protection]	4.2727	.80128	4.0769	1.06090	4.2143	.87590
10a. How significant are the following obstacles in the	4.0606	.78817	4.1026	1.02070	3.8571	1.00791

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intellectual property protection system? [d] Lack of harmonization with international IP standards]						
10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [a] Harmonizing national IP laws with international standards]	4.3030	.68396	4.2051	.83286	3.9286	1.05158
10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [b] Encouraging innovation while ensuring fair competition]	4.3636	.69903	4.5128	.60139	4.3571	.82616
10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [c] Addressing piracy and counterfeiting effectively]	4.4545	.61699	4.4103	.63734	4.2500	.96705
10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [d] Promoting cross-border cooperation and information sharing]	4.1212	.78093	4.2308	.95866	4.1786	1.02030
10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [e] Balancing the interests of IP holders with public access to knowledge]	4.1212	.64988	4.0513	.88700	3.8929	.99403

Source: Authors' presentation

As well previous results and the analysis of the average ratings of the variables achieved by country, shows enviable results, since in most cases in the analysed countries the average ratings are above 4. The differences by the countries are analysed and presented in the next table. The lowest rated variables in Albania are: 6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [c] Subsidies for technology commercialization efforts] (3.80); 6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [a] Tax credits and deductions for research and development activities] (3.88); 6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [d] Regulatory support and streamlined processes for intellectual property protection] (3.88). Managers in Bosnia and Herzegovina the lowest marks gave to variable 1. What are the key actors of an open innovation

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ecosystem? [c] Government bodies that support funding and policy] (3.52), 7. How do you perform R&D activities? [a] Collaboration with universities and external partners] (3.28) and 7. How do you perform R&D activities? [b] Establishing research centers focused on innovation] (3.04), while the lowest marks in North Macedonia are for variables 1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [c] Government bodies that support funding and policy] (3.84); 8. How do you implement innovative solutions in your company (organization)? [b] We engage external experts to support innovation] (3.72) and 7. How do you perform R&D activities? [b] Establishing research centers focused on innovation] (3.56). In Serbia, the lowest marks were given to variables 8. How do you implement innovative solutions in your company (organization)? [b] We engage external experts to support innovation] (3.56) and 6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [c] Subsidies for technology commercialization efforts] (3.92).

Table 8: Average ratings by country

Country	Albania		Bosnia and Herzegovina		North Macedonia		Serbia	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [a] Universities and research institutions]	4.4400	.76811	3.8000	1.08012	4.4800	.77028	4.4800	.58595
1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [b] Start-ups, small and medium-sized enterprises, and large corporations]	4.3600	.81035	4.1600	.89815	4.3200	.74833	4.4400	.71181
1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [c] Government bodies that support funding and policy]	4.2400	.87939	3.5200	1.32665	3.8400	.98658	4.2000	.81650
1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [d] Investors]	4.0800	.90921	4.4000	.95743	4.3200	.74833	4.2000	1.00000

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2. How much are the following aspects important for the implementation of open innovation strategies? [a] Innovation culture within the organization]	4.4800	.65320	4.2000	.86603	4.6800	.62716	4.5600	.58310
2. How much are the following aspects important for the implementation of open innovation strategies? [b] Technological infrastructure]	4.3600	.63770	4.3200	.62716	4.5200	.65320	4.3600	.75719
2. How much are the following aspects important for the implementation of open innovation strategies? [c] Leadership and management support]	4.4400	.65064	4.4000	.95743	4.6000	.64550	4.7200	.45826
3. How much are the following factors important for successful commercialization of innovations? [a] Market access and marketing orientation of the organization]	4.3600	.70000	4.4000	.70711	4.4000	.70711	4.6400	.48990
3. How much are the following factors important for successful commercialization of innovations? [b] Intellectual	4.2800	.93630	4.0800	.95394	4.3600	.81035	4.2400	.83066

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property protection (patents protection, copyrights, trade secrets, industrial design rights, trademarks and branding)]								
3. How much are the following factors important for successful commercialization of innovations? [c) Product adaptation to market needs]	4.5600	.58310	4.5600	.58310	4.6400	.56862	4.4800	.71414
3. How much are the following factors important for successful commercialization of innovations? [d) Partnerships with industrial entities]	4.1200	1.09240	4.1600	.94340	4.4800	.65320	4.0000	.81650
4. What are the main challenges of technology transfer and sustainable entrepreneurship in the open innovation ecosystem in your country? [a) Insufficient financial resources and investments]	4.1600	1.06771	4.2000	.70711	4.4800	.82260	4.0000	.81650
4. What are the main challenges of technology transfer and sustainable entrepreneurship in the open innovation ecosystem in your country? [b) Weak collaboration between industry	4.4000	.76376	4.1200	1.05357	4.3600	.70000	3.9600	.97809

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and research institutions]								
5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [a] Availability of grants and subsidies]	4.3200	.80208	4.0000	1.04083	4.4000	.70711	4.0400	.78951
5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [b] Opportunities for private investment]	4.2800	.79162	4.3200	.80208	4.2000	.76376	4.0800	.70238
5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [c] Access to angels' investors, venture capital and crowdfunding]	4.0800	.70238	3.7600	1.09087	4.2000	.81650	4.0800	.81240
5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [d] Tax incentives for research and development]	4.2000	.70711	3.9200	1.03763	4.0800	.95394	4.2800	.67823
5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [e] Costs	4.4400	.71181	4.3600	.95219	4.3600	.75719	4.2400	.83066

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and return on investment]								
6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [a] Tax credits and deductions for research and development activities]	3.8800	1.16619	3.9200	1.03763	4.1600	.68799	4.0400	.84063
6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [b] Grants and funding programs for collaborative research projects]	4.1600	.89815	4.0000	1.15470	4.6000	.64550	4.1200	.83267
6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [c] Subsidies for technology commercialization efforts]	3.8000	.95743	4.0000	1.15470	4.4000	.81650	3.9200	.81240
6. To what extent are the following government incentives	3.8800	1.01325	4.1200	.92736	3.9600	.97809	4.1600	.89815

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important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [d] Regulatory support and streamlined processes for intellectual property protection]									
7. How do you perform R&D activities? [a] Collaboration with universities and external partners]	4.0400	1.27410	3.2800	1.36991	4.0000	1.08012	4.1600	.85049	
7. How do you perform R&D activities? [b] Establishing research centers focused on innovation]	4.0000	1.00000	3.0400	1.24097	3.5600	1.19304	4.2800	.93630	
7. How do you perform R&D activities? [c] Conducting market research to guide product development]	4.2000	.64550	4.0000	1.00000	4.4400	.58310	4.2000	.76376	
7. How do you perform R&D activities? [d] Participation in collaborative research projects with global partners]	4.4000	.76376	3.9600	1.17189	3.9200	1.03763	4.0000	1.11803	
8. How do you implement innovative solutions in your company (organization)? [a] We use internal	4.2000	.76376	4.0400	1.13578	4.5200	.65320	4.2800	.84261	

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R&D teams for developing new solutions]								
8. How do you implement innovative solutions in your company (organization)? [b] We engage external experts to support innovation]	3.9600	.97809	3.7600	1.01160	3.7200	1.10000	3.5600	1.12101
9. How much are the following legal and regulatory factors important for the intellectual property protection? [c] National intellectual property laws]	4.1600	.89815	4.3600	.75719	4.3600	.81035	4.2000	.86603
9. How much are the following legal and regulatory factors important for the intellectual property protection? [d] International agreements and conventions]	4.2000	.64550	4.3200	.94516	4.4000	.81650	4.2800	.73711
9. How much are the following legal and regulatory factors important for the intellectual property protection? [e] Administrative procedures for rights protection]	4.2000	.64550	4.2400	.96954	4.1600	.89815	4.5600	.65064
10a. How significant are the following obstacles in the intellectual	4.2000	.81650	4.0400	1.09848	4.2400	.96954	4.3200	.62716

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property protection system? [a] High costs and complexity of the patent system]								
10a. How significant are the following obstacles in the intellectual property protection system? [b] Lack of awareness and education on intellectual property rights]	4.2800	.89069	4.1600	1.06771	4.2800	.93630	4.1200	.78102
10a. How significant are the following obstacles in the intellectual property protection system? [c] Insufficient enforcement mechanisms for IP protection]	4.1200	.88129	4.1600	1.02794	4.3200	1.02956	4.1200	.78102
10a. How significant are the following obstacles in the intellectual property protection system? [d] Lack of harmonization with international IP standards]	3.9200	.86217	4.0800	1.11505	4.0800	.99666	4.0000	.81650
10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [a] Harmonizing national IP laws with international standards]	4.2400	.83066	4.0800	1.03763	4.3600	.63770	3.9600	.88882

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10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [b] Encouraging innovation while ensuring fair competition]	4.3600	.70000	4.4000	.91287	4.6000	.50000	4.3200	.62716
10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [c] Addressing piracy and counterfeiting effectively]	4.3600	.56862	4.3600	.95219	4.6800	.47610	4.1200	.78102
10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [d] Promoting cross-border cooperation and information sharing]	4.1200	.72572	4.2000	1.04083	4.2400	1.01160	4.1600	.89815
10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [e] Balancing the interests of IP holders with public access to knowledge]	4.0800	.70238	4.0800	1.03763	3.9600	1.01980	4.0000	.57735

Source: Authors' presentation

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The analysis of the results based on the respondents' gender is presented in the next table. For the great number of variables, the average ratings given by women are lower than average ratings given by men (only 27.5% variables were rated higher from the women point of view). Only the following 11 variables received higher average ratings from women compared to men: 1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [a] Universities and research institutions] (4.43 rating from women and 4.21 rating from men); 1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [b] Start-ups, small and medium-sized enterprises, and large corporations] (4.33 rating from women and 4.31 rating from men); 1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [c] Government bodies that support funding and policy] (4.30 rating from women and 3.72 rating from men); 2. How much are the following aspects important for the implementation of open innovation strategies? [b] Technological infrastructure] (4.46 rating from women and 4.34 rating from men); 2. How much are the following aspects important for the implementation of open innovation strategies? [c] Leadership and management support] (4.46 rating from women and 4.59 rating from men); 3. How much are the following factors important for successful commercialization of innovations? [a] Market access and marketing orientation of the organization] (4.46 rating from women and 4.44 rating from men); 5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [a] Availability of grants and subsidies] (4.28 rating from women and 4.13 rating from men); 5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [b] Opportunities for private investment] (4.28 rating from women and 4.18 rating from men); 5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [c] Access to angles' investors, venture capital and crowdfunding] (4.13 rating from women and 3.97 rating from men); 9. How much are the following legal and regulatory factors important for the intellectual property protection? [e] Administrative procedures for rights protection] (4.33 rating from women and 4.26 rating from men); 10a. How significant are the following obstacles in the intellectual property protection system? [b] Lack of awareness and education on intellectual property rights] (4.13 rating from women and 4.24 rating from men). Greater differences in the ratings given by men and women are present in the case of 1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [c] Government bodies that support funding and policy] (4.31 rating from women and 3.72 rating from men) and 8. How do you implement innovative solutions in your company (organization)? [b] We engage external experts to support innovation] (3.46 rating from women and 3.93 rating from men).

Table 9: Average ratings according to gender of the respondents

Gender	Female		Male	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [a] Universities and research institutions]	4.4359	.68036	4.2131	.95070
1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [b] Start-ups, small and medium-sized enterprises, and large corporations]	4.3333	.80568	4.3115	.78615
1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [c] Government bodies that support funding and policy]	4.3077	.76619	3.7213	1.14209
1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem? [d] Investors]	4.2051	.80064	4.2787	.96835

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2. How much are the following aspects important for the implementation of open innovation strategies? [a] Innovation culture within the organization]	4.3077	.73104	4.5902	.66776
2. How much are the following aspects important for the implementation of open innovation strategies? [b] Technological infrastructure]	4.4615	.64262	4.3443	.68032
2. How much are the following aspects important for the implementation of open innovation strategies? [c] Leadership and management support]	4.4615	.71987	4.5902	.69227
3. How much are the following factors important for successful commercialization of innovations? [a] Market access and marketing orientation of the organization]	4.4615	.68234	4.4426	.64613
3. How much are the following factors important for successful commercialization of innovations? [b] Intellectual property protection (patents protection, copyrights, trade secrets, industrial design rights, trademarks and branding)]	4.2051	.80064	4.2623	.92919
3. How much are the following factors important for successful commercialization of innovations? [c] Product adaptation to market needs]	4.4103	.67738	4.6557	.54422
3. How much are the following factors important for successful commercialization of innovations? [d] Partnerships with industrial entities]	4.1538	.90433	4.2131	.89656
4. What are the main challenges of technology transfer and sustainable entrepreneurship in the open innovation ecosystem in your country? [a] Insufficient financial resources and investments]	4.2051	.92280	4.2131	.83894
4. What are the main challenges of technology transfer and sustainable entrepreneurship in the open innovation ecosystem in your country? [b] Weak collaboration between industry and research institutions]	4.1282	.89382	4.2623	.89259
5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [a] Availability of grants and subsidies]	4.2821	.85682	4.1311	.84608
5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [b] Opportunities for private investment]	4.2821	.72361	4.1803	.78546
5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [c] Access to angles' investors, venture capital and crowdfunding]	4.1282	.92280	3.9672	.83601
5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [d] Tax incentives for research and development]	4.3077	.73104	4.0000	.91287

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5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer? [e] Costs and return on investment]	4.2051	.76707	4.4426	.82714
6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [a] Tax credits and deductions for research and development activities]	3.8718	.97817	4.0820	.91824
6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [b] Grants and funding programs for collaborative research projects]	4.1538	.90433	4.2623	.92919
6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [c] Subsidies for technology commercialization efforts]	3.9487	.97194	4.0820	.95385
6. To what extent are the following government incentives important for supporting collaboration in technology transfer? [d] Regulatory support and streamlined processes for intellectual property protection]	3.8718	1.00471	4.1311	.90324
7. How do you perform R&D activities? [a] Collaboration with universities and external partners]	3.8205	1.21117	3.9016	1.19310
7. How do you perform R&D activities? [b] Establishing research centers focused on innovation]	3.7179	1.09901	3.7213	1.24004
7. How do you perform R&D activities? [c] Conducting market research to guide product development]	4.0513	.79302	4.3115	.74254
7. How do you perform R&D activities? [d] Participation in collaborative research projects with global partners]	3.8974	1.02070	4.1803	1.04096
8. How do you implement innovative solutions in your company (organization)? [a] We use internal R&D teams for developing new solutions]	4.1795	.88472	4.3115	.86681
8. How do you implement innovative solutions in your company (organization)? [b] We engage external experts to support innovation]	3.4615	1.04746	3.9344	1.01438
9. How much are the following legal and regulatory factors important for the intellectual property protection? [c] National intellectual property laws]	4.1795	.79046	4.3279	.85091
9. How much are the following legal and regulatory factors important for the intellectual property protection? [d] International agreements and conventions]	4.2821	.72361	4.3115	.82747
9. How much are the following legal and regulatory factors important for the intellectual property protection? [e] Administrative procedures for rights protection]	4.3333	.62126	4.2623	.91107

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10a. How significant are the following obstacles in the intellectual property protection system? [a] High costs and complexity of the patent system]	4.1282	.73196	4.2459	.97734
10a. How significant are the following obstacles in the intellectual property protection system? [b] Lack of awareness and education on intellectual property rights]	4.2308	.87243	4.1967	.94551
10a. How significant are the following obstacles in the intellectual property protection system? [c] Insufficient enforcement mechanisms for IP protection]	4.0256	.98641	4.2787	.87809
10a. How significant are the following obstacles in the intellectual property protection system? [d] Lack of harmonization with international IP standards]	3.8974	.99459	4.0984	.90747
10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [a] Harmonizing national IP laws with international standards]	3.9487	.94448	4.2951	.78197
10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [b] Encouraging innovation while ensuring fair competition]	4.3333	.66227	4.4754	.72126
10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [c] Addressing piracy and counterfeiting effectively]	4.1282	.69508	4.5410	.72050
10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [d] Promoting cross-border cooperation and information sharing]	4.1795	.88472	4.1803	.94000
10b. How significant are the following challenges of the intellectual property protection system? [e] Balancing the interests of IP holders with public access to knowledge]	3.9487	.72361	4.0820	.91824

Source: Authors' presentation